

Trustworthy Reputation for Federated Learning Leveraging Blockchain: A Demonstration

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Abstract—The inherent virtualization characteristics of 5G, 6G, and subsequent generations (xG) facilitate the modularity of components and their interfaces, leading to an increase in the number of stakeholders and necessitating more complex administrative relationships. In this demonstration, we present an open-source Decentralized Application (DApp) integrated with smart contracts deployed on a live Polygon testnet to support trustworthy Federated Learning (FL). FL enables clients to conduct local training and updates, while a central aggregation server processes these inputs for global FL training. We introduce a blockchain-based reputation system within such FL model to facilitate collaborative training of Machine Learning (ML) models. The deployed smart contracts on the Layer 2 Polygon blockchain calculate and store reputation scores on-chain for each FL client based on their contribution. This demonstration presents a visualization of the blockchain network parameters during the execution of blockchain-enabled smart contracts. The DApp offers an interactive interface for client registration, performance parameter submission, and reputation score calculation. We use Alchemy’s dashboard for real-time monitoring of blockchain transactions and smart contract interactions. The open-source implementation is publicly available¹ and the video of the demo is available at².

Index Terms—Blockchain, smart contracts, trust, Federated Learning, Reputation, Polygon, EVM

I. INTRODUCTION

Next-generation mobile networks (5G, 6G, and beyond) are adopting virtualized, modular architectures that replace traditional monolithic structures with disaggregated network functions and defined interfaces. This shift enhances flexibility and customization but also increases the number of stakeholders, requiring complex administrative relationships to ensure interoperability and coordination. For example, the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) initiative exemplifies this shift by promoting open, virtualized, and disaggregated RAN components [1] as O-RAN represents a significant move from conventional, proprietary RAN architectures to

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¹<https://github.com/farhanajaved/bc-fl-demo-12>

²<https://youtu.be/B9J1gxjoKdM>

Figure 1: Proposed Framework and Components

an open and disaggregated approach. It supports multi-vendor interoperability and leverages software solutions for enhanced performance through closed-loop operations. This allows each stakeholder to manage local network functions and generate environment-specific data. Addressing data privacy alone does not tackle the broader issues of trust and accountability in a multi-vendor environment. Even with local data retention, the risk of low-quality or malicious updates compromising model performance remains. Without a transparent system to verify and reward dependable contributions, federated training efforts are prone to hidden risks. Therefore, ensuring the credibility and auditability of each stakeholder’s updates is essential for achieving effective collaborative intelligence [2], [3].

In such use cases, where Federated Learning (FL) optimizes operations in diverse mobile networks by enabling stakeholders to train local models with their own data without sharing it [4] an aggregator combines these models into a global model. This model is then redistributed to enhance operations while maintaining data privacy and reducing communication overhead. This global model is subsequently redistributed to the clients for further training in additional rounds. This ongoing cycle continually improves the model’s accuracy and efficacy over time. Thus, FL supports collaborative intelligence in next-generation, multi-stakeholder mobile networks [5]. However, an approach that enables collaborative intelligence without compromising data privacy and enabling trust is essential.

The proposed framework illustrated in Figure 1 combines the strengths of FL and blockchain technology to enable collaborative learning environments [6]. In this setup, FL clients and a central server conduct decentralized training. Each client independently develops a local model aimed at precisely predicting resource needs. Performance is evaluated using low Normalized Mean Squared Error (NMSE) to ensure fair and accurate contributions. To further enhance system reliability, blockchain technology is integrated as a decentralized and immutable ledger. This allows for the secure recording and verification of all model contributions and updates on the blockchain, enabling trustworthiness and transparency [7].

By utilizing the Layer 2 Polygon blockchain and its testnet³, along with Hardhat⁴ and Alchemy Node⁵ for deploying smart contracts, we demonstrate reputation calculation using smart contracts. Our proposed work uses the live testnet to provide a realistic testing environment, contrasting with the static deployments commonly found in existing literature. Testing on the Polygon testnet provides a realistic setting that closely mimics mainnet conditions, offering a more accurate alternative to simulators like Ganache.

II. PROPOSED WORK

Building on the MonB5G project⁶, our proposed work introduces a blockchain-based framework to support trustworthy reputation calculations for FL in multi-stakeholder environments. As detailed in [8], the FL setup in MonB5G involves client registration, local model training, NMSE evaluation, and the aggregation of model updates to refine the global model. This ensures that all participants can trust the integrity and fairness of contributions to the collaborative process [9].

To orchestrate the FL process on the blockchain, we have developed three smart contracts on the live Polygon testnet: `registrationClient.sol` for onboarding authorized participants, `weightSubmission.sol` for

handling NMSE submissions with assured blockchain integrity, and `reputationCalculation.sol` for computing reputation scores based on client contributions. Furthermore, by utilizing Chainlink’s `OracleSmartContract` and a custom external adapter, we integrate external data sources by retrieving client data from a mock API and feeding it into `WeightSubmission.sol`. The `reputationCalculation.sol` contract then selects the top 90% of performers for aggregating the global model in the next training round, ensuring high-quality contributions and enhancing transparency and trust through clearly defined, immutable selection criteria within the smart contracts integrated into a Decentralized Application (DApp). This work is demonstration of our work presented in [10].

III. DEMONSTRATION

This demonstration showcases the real-time interaction of our proposed smart contracts within our FL DApp on the live Polygon testnet. Deploying our smart contracts on this testnet provides a realistic and actively maintained environment similar to the Polygon mainnet, an L2 blockchain. The Amoy testnet, introduced for the Polygon Proof of Stake (PoS) network, serves as a blockchain testing environment designed to facilitate the development, testing, and refinement of applications. Upon executing transactions on the Amoy testnet, developers gain comprehensive access to various data and insights relevant to their DApps’ performance. This test environment allows for real-time monitoring and analysis of DApp transactions, providing detailed insights into functionality under varied conditions. Key metrics tracked include transaction status, gas consumption, block confirmations, and error diagnostics. The Amoy testnet also includes tools to analyze smart contract states and logs, aiding developers in debugging and optimizing applications before deployment on the main network.

To demonstrate the core functionalities of our FL system, we will conduct a live demonstration focusing on three essential smart contracts deployed on the Layer 2 Polygon testnet: one for FL participant onboarding, another for managing local NMSE value submissions, and a third for calculating reputation scores based on client contributions. We will deploy these contracts, with real-time deployment logs displayed as shown in Figure 2. Throughout the demonstration, Alchemy’s dashboard will serve as a comprehensive platform for testing blockchain applications, offering developers the necessary tools to streamline the processes of building, deploying, and managing DApps across multiple blockchain networks. This includes testing environments for smart contracts and DApps to ensure they function correctly before deployment. Additionally, it offers a live visualization of all transactions, along with detailed insights into smart contract interactions and script executions.

Upon deploying the framework, gas usage and latency are critical parameters to observe. Initially, clients submit NMSE

³<https://amoy.polygonscan.com/>, Accessed on 10th November 2024

⁴<https://hardhat.org/>, Accessed on 31st January 2025

⁵<https://www.alchemy.com/>, Accessed on 31st January 2025

⁶<https://www.monb5g.eu/>: Accessed on 10th November 2024

Figure 2: Layout of the Graphical Visualization of the Demonstration

values via smart contracts, consuming 113,394 gas for the first submission and 96,294 gas for subsequent submissions. During experimentation we also observed that the average gas price stands at 1.5 Gwei, with each block accommodating approximately 3 transactions and measuring around 2.61KB. In terms of latency, the registration process averages 9.6 seconds. NMSE submission latency scales linearly with the number of submissions, and updates to reputation scores, calculated using $R_i = \frac{1 \times 10^{18}}{NMSE_i + 10}$, take about 6.7 seconds [10].

IV. CONCLUSION

The demonstration showcases an approach to integrating blockchain technology with Federated Learning (FL) to enhance trust and accountability in multi-vendor mobile network environments. The demonstration primarily focuses on showcasing a Decentralized Application (DApp) that uses smart contracts deployed on the Polygon testnet to manage and verify the contributions of various stakeholders in a collaborative machine learning process. The deployment strategy for this framework involves utilizing the Amoy testnet of the Polygon blockchain, allowing for real-time interaction, testing, and refinement of the application under conditions that closely mimic the main network. This strategy provides a realistic and actively maintained testing environment, which is crucial for the accurate evaluation of the application. This approach enables trustworthiness by providing a transparent and immutable ledger for recording all contributions to the machine learning models. By doing so, it ensures that each contribution can be audited and verified, which is essential for maintaining the integrity of the collaborative process. The use of blockchain technology in this manner not only

enhances the trustworthiness of the federated learning process but also optimizes operations by allowing stakeholders to independently train local models without compromising data privacy.

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